

Life Expectancy Without Limitations in Italian Regions

It grew by an average of 15.21% between 2008 and 2019

ISTAT-BES calculates life expectancy without limitations in activities at 65. This indicator expresses the average number of years that a 65-year-old person can expect to live without being restricted in activities due to health problems, using the share of people who responded that they have had limitations, for at least 6 months, due to problems health in carrying out the activities that people usually carry out. The data are available between 2008 and 2019.

Ranking of the Italian regions by life expectancy without limitations in activities at 65 years in 2019. Valle d'Aosta is in first place for the value of life expectancy without limitation in activities at 65 years with an amount equal to 11.9 units, followed by Trentino-Alto Adige with a value of 11.4 units and by Piedmont with an amount of 10.9 units. In the middle of the table there are Emilia-Romagna with an amount equal to 10.5, followed by Veneto with an amount equal to 10.4 and Umbria with an amount equal to 10.2 units. Campania closes the ranking with an amount of 8.8 units, followed by Calabria with a value of 8.5 units and Sicily with a value of 7.8 units. On average, a 65-year-old person in 2019 could expect to live about 10 years without severe limitations in carrying out daily activities.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in life expectancy without limitation at 65 years between 2008 and 2019. Sardinia is in first place by value of the percentage change in life expectancy without limitations at 65 years with an amount equal to 31.43% equal to a value of 2.2 units, followed by Calabria with an amount equal to 30.77% equal to an amount of 2 units and by Sicily with a value equal to 21.88% equal to 1.4 unit. In the middle of the table there are Campania with an amount equal to 17.33% equal to an amount of 1.3 years, followed by Basilicata with an amount of 15.58% equal to an amount of 1.2 units and Friuli- Venezia Giulia with a change equal to an amount of 14.74% equal to an amount of 1.4 units. Veneto closes the ranking with an amount equal to 6.12% equal to an amount of 0.6 units, followed by Umbria with an amount equal to 3.03% equal to a value of 0.3 units and Piedmont with a value equal to 1.87% equal to an amount of 0.2 units. On average for the 20 Italian regions between 2008 and 2019, the value of life expectancy without limitations grew by an amount equal to 15.21% or approximately 1.26 years.

Italian Macro-Regions. Unlimited life expectancy at 65 grew between 2008 and 2009 in the Italian macro-regions. In Northern Italy life expectancy without limitations at 65 years has increased from an amount of 10.00 units up to a value of 10.70 units or equal to a value of 0.70 units equal to an amount of 7.00%. In Central Italy, unrestricted life expectancy at 65 years has increased from an amount of 9.00 years to a value of 10.20 years or equal to a variation of 1.20 years equal to a value of 13.33 %. In the South, life expectancy without limitations at 65 years is growing from an amount of 7.20 years up to a value of 8.70 years or a growth of 1.50 years equal to a value of 20.83%. Overall, in Italy, life expectancy without limitations at 65 years has increased from an amount of 8.90 years to a value of 10.00 years or equal to a value of 1.10 years equal to a value of 12.36 %. Overall, it is possible to detect the presence of a gap between the Center-North on the one hand and Southern Italy.

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In fact, in Northern Italy the unrestricted life expectancy at 65 is about 2 years higher than in the South, while the difference between the Center and the South is 1.5 years. It clearly follows those differences in per capita income and in the quality of health services, together with lifestyles, have a very significant impact in determining the regional gaps between Southern, Central and Northern Italy.

Correlation matrix. A correlation matrix is presented below, having as an attention variable life expectancy without limitations in activities at 65 years. It turns out that this value is positively associated with:

- Healthy life expectancy at birth with a correlation index of 0.7;
- Life expectancy at birth with a correlation index equal to a value of 0.6;
- Mortality due to dementia and diseases of the nervous system with a correlation index equal to 0.5;
- Adequate nutrition with a correlation index equal to a value of 0.5;
- Alcohol with a correlation index equal to a value of 0.4;

In addition, unrestricted life expectancy at 65 years is negatively associated with the following variables, namely:

- Mortality from road accidents with a correlation index value of 0.0;
- Smoking with a correlation index of -0.1;
- Cancer mortality with a correlation index -0.2;
- Infant mortality with a correlation index -0.5;
- Excess weight with a correlation index -0.6;
- Sedentary lifestyle with a correlation index of -0.7.

It therefore follows that among the elements that positively affect the expectation without limitations at 65, together with context variables, there is adequate nutrition. On the contrary, the elements that reduce the healthy life expectancy at 65 are sedentary lifestyle with a value equal to -0.7 units, excess weight with a value equal to -0.6 units and smoking, with a value of -0.1 units. The elements connected to the habits of individual life have a very relevant value in the possibility of having a life without limitations at the age of 65.

Clusterization with k-Means algorithm: Silhouette coefficient vs Elbow method. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. The data show the presence of two clusters identified as follows:

- Cluster 1: Piedmont, Lombardy, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Trentino-Alto Adige, Tuscany, Liguria, Veneto, Emilia-Romagna, Marche, Molise, Abruzzo, Lazio, Umbria;
- Cluster 2: Sicily, Calabria, Campania, Sardinia, Puglia, Basilicata.

By calculating the median of the clusters, it results that the median value of the regions of cluster 1 is equal to an amount of 10.6 units, while the value of the median of cluster 2 is equal to a value of 9.2 units. It therefore follows that $C1 = 10.6 > C2 = 9.2$. Therefore, the unrestricted life expectancy at 65 years in the C1 regions is approximately 1.4 years higher - considering the median of the cluster. However, repeating the calculations with the Elbow method it results that the optimal number of clusters is equal to 3. Therefore, the clustering model is repeated with the following results, that is:

- Cluster 1: Umbria, Lazio, Molise, Abruzzo, Basilicata, Puglia;

- Cluster 2: Lombardy, Piedmont, Liguria, Trentino-Alto Adige, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Tuscany, Valle d'Aosta, Emilia-Romagna, Veneto, Marche;
- Cluster 3: Sicily, Calabria, Campania, Sardinia.

Therefore, recalculating the median of the clusters results in the following ordering of clusters, that is: $C2 = 10.8 > C1 = 9.7 > C3 = 8.65$. This clustering model suggested by the Elbow method is preferred to the previous one indicated by the Silhouette method, as it has a greater ability to grasp the elements of the territorial complexity of the Italian regions. In fact, from a geographical point of view, it appears that life expectancy without limitations at 65 years is higher in Northern Italy than in Central Italy and compared to the South. There are some regions of the South, such as Puglia that perform with the cluster of regions of central Italy.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Below is a comparison between eight different machine learning algorithms for predicting the value of life expectancy without limitations at 65 years. The algorithms were trained with 70% of the data while the remaining 30% was used for actual prediction. The algorithms are evaluated based on their ability to maximize the R-square and minimize the main statistical errors or "Mean Absolute Error", "Root Mean Squared Error", "Mean Squared Error". The results are shown below:

- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 4;
- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff value of 8;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 12;
- Tree Ensemble Regression with a payoff value of 16;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 20;
- Gradient Boosted Trees Regression with a payoff value of 24;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 28;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 32.

The prediction based on the use of the Random Forest Regression algorithm is shown below, namely:

- Piedmont with a decrease from an amount of 10.9 units up to a value of 9.50 units or equal to a variation of -1.40 units equal to an amount of -12.83%;
- Valle d'Aosta with a decrease from an amount of 11.9 units up to a value of 7.97 units or equal to a value of -3.93 units equal to a variation of -33.00%;
- Lombardy with a decrease from an amount of 10.8 to a value of 10.08 units or equal to a variation of -0.72 units equal to a value of -6.69%;
- Lazio with a confirmed value of 9.7;
- Basilicata with an increase from an amount of 8.9 units up to a value of 11.36 units or equal to a variation of 2.46 units equal to a value of 27.61%.

Overall, the value of life expectancy without limitation for the regions indicated is predicted to decrease from an average value of 10.44 years up to a value of 9.72 years or a reduction equal to a value of -0.71 equal to at a value of -6.8%.

Conclusions. The value of unrestricted life expectancy at 65 has grown in all Italian macro-regions. However, there are significant differences between North, Center and South. The gap between Italian macro-regions indicates that income differences and the efficiency of local health systems play some role in extending life expectancy without limitations to 65 years. However, it is likely that following the covid and in the presence of inflation there will be a reduction in life expectancy without

limitations to 65 years as a manifestation of the incipient recession and the reduction in accessibility of health services.

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Appendix

	2019	Feature 1	Cluster
1	10.9	Piemonte	C2
2	11.9	Valle d'Aosta/V...	C2
3	10.6	Liguria	C2
4	10.8	Lombardia	C2
5	11.4	Trentino-Alto A...	C2
6	10.4	Veneto	C2
7	10.9	Friuli-Venezia G...	C2
8	10.5	Emilia-Romagna	C2
9	10.6	Toscana	C2
10	10.2	Umbria	C1
11	10.8	Marche	C2
12	9.7	Lazio	C1
13	9.7	Abruzzo	C1
14	10.1	Molise	C1
15	8.8	Campania	C3
16	9.2	Puglia	C1
17	8.9	Basilicata	C1
18	8.5	Calabria	C3
19	7.8	Sicilia	C3
20	9.2	Sardegna	C3

Matrice di correlazione

Variabile	A
Speranza di vita alla nascita	1
Speranza di vita in buona salute alla nascita	2
Indice di salute mentale (SF36)	3
Mortalità infantile	4
Mortalità per incidenti stradali (15-34 anni)	5
Mortalità per tumore (20-64 anni)	6
Mortalità per demenze e malattie del sistema nervoso (65 anni e più)	7
Speranza di vita senza limitazioni nelle attività a 65 anni	8
Eccesso di peso	9
Fumo	10
Alcol	11
Sedentarietà	12
Adeguata alimentazione	13

	2019	Prediction 2019	Var Ass	Var Per
Piemonte	★ 10,9	★ 9,50	★ -1,40	★ -12,83
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	★ 11,9	★ 7,97	★ -3,93	★ -33,00
Lombardia	★ 10,8	★ 10,08	★ -0,72	★ -6,69
Lazio	★ 9,7	★ 9,70	★ 0,00	★ 0,00
Basilicata	★ 8,9	★ 11,36	★ 2,46	★ 27,61
Media	★ 10,44	★ 9,721793379	★ -0,718	★ -6,879

	R^2	mean absolute error	mean squared error	root mean squared error
ANN	0,90357619	0,066245402	0,012201779	0,110461662
PNN	0,78011683	0,117283951	0,031398248	0,177195508
Simple Regression Tree	0,18703398	0,221754976	0,074352719	0,27267695
Gradient Boosted Trees Regression	0,2063975	0,234680196	0,075882676	0,275468104
Random Forest Regression	0,95294262	0,064536764	0,006683255	0,081751178
Tree Ensemble Regression	0,74830803	0,136952381	0,03281698	0,181154574
Linear Regression	0,74463414	0,115922285	0,025926496	0,161017068
Polynomial Regression	-2	0,518518519	0,386374028	0,62158992

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Piemonte	★ 10,7	★ 10,2	★ 10,3	★ 10,3	★ 10,8	★ 9,9	★ 10,7	★ 10,9	★ 10,7	★ 10,4	★ 10,8	★ 10,9
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	★ 9,9	★ 9,6	★ 8,7	★ 10	★ 11,1	★ 10,4	★ 11,2	★ 8,8	★ 11	★ 11,9	★ 10,6	★ 11,9
Liguria	★ 9,8	★ 10,2	★ 10,5	★ 10,9	★ 10	★ 10,2	★ 11,2	★ 10	★ 11,4	★ 10,6	★ 11,2	★ 10,6
Lombardia	★ 10	★ 9,7	★ 10,4	★ 10,4	★ 9,9	★ 10,4	★ 10,6	★ 11,4	★ 11,4	★ 10,8	★ 10,7	★ 10,8
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	★ 9,6	★ 10	★ 11	★ 10,5	★ 11,3	★ 10,4	★ 10,8	★ 10,7	★ 10,3	★ 10,7	★ 11	★ 11,4
Veneto	★ 9,8	★ 9,4	★ 8,7	★ 9,7	★ 10,6	★ 9,5	★ 10,1	★ 10,7	★ 10,5	★ 10,3	★ 10,7	★ 10,4
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ 9,5	★ 9,6	★ 10,6	★ 9,6	★ 10,3	★ 10,6	★ 10,5	★ 11	★ 11,4	★ 10,5	★ 10,2	★ 10,9
Emilia-Romagna	★ 9,7	★ 9,9	★ 9,6	★ 9,2	★ 9,3	★ 11,2	★ 11,7	★ 9,8	★ 10,9	★ 10,3	★ 10	★ 10,5
Toscana	★ 9,3	★ 9,7	★ 9,4	★ 9,6	★ 10,7	★ 10,5	★ 10	★ 11,3	★ 10,9	★ 10,9	★ 10,5	★ 10,6
Umbria	★ 9,9	★ 7,8	★ 7,9	★ 8,5	★ 9,3	★ 9	★ 10,2	★ 10,9	★ 8,8	★ 8,8	★ 8,7	★ 10,2
Marche	★ 9,2	★ 8,7	★ 9,7	★ 10,9	★ 11,3	★ 9,7	★ 10,3	★ 8,7	★ 10,2	★ 11,1	★ 10,3	★ 10,8
Lazio	★ 8,5	★ 7,9	★ 8,3	★ 8,6	★ 10,6	★ 8,8	★ 9,3	★ 9,6	★ 9,5	★ 9,2	★ 10,4	★ 9,7
Abruzzo	★ 8,5	★ 8,4	★ 8,9	★ 10,6	★ 8,9	★ 8,6	★ 9,7	★ 9,4	★ 8,6	★ 10	★ 10,5	★ 9,7
Molise	★ 8,6	★ 7,9	★ 7,6	★ 8,3	★ 9,9	★ 8,8	★ 11,3	★ 9,7	★ 9,3	★ 10,4	★ 10,1	★ 10,1
Campania	★ 7,5	★ 8	★ 7,3	★ 7,5	★ 7,2	★ 6,9	★ 7,3	★ 6,8	★ 7,9	★ 6,8	★ 8,1	★ 8,8
Puglia	★ 7,6	★ 7,7	★ 7,7	★ 8,6	★ 8,8	★ 7,6	★ 8,7	★ 8,7	★ 9	★ 9,9	★ 9	★ 9,2
Basilicata	★ 7,7	★ 9,7	★ 7,8	★ 9,8	★ 7,9	★ 7,9	★ 9,6	★ 9,4	★ 8,9	★ 7,9	★ 7,9	★ 8,9
Calabria	★ 6,5	★ 7	★ 6,9	★ 6,6	★ 8,3	★ 6,7	★ 7,4	★ 7,7	★ 7,5	★ 6,6	★ 7,9	★ 8,5
Sicilia	★ 6,4	★ 6,9	★ 7,1	★ 7,4	★ 7,7	★ 7,7	★ 7,6	★ 7,4	★ 7,3	★ 7,3	★ 8,3	★ 7,8
Sardegna	★ 7	★ 7,1	★ 8,5	★ 7,2	★ 8,8	★ 8	★ 7,1	★ 9,2	★ 7,8	★ 9,7	★ 9	★ 9,2

Plot of total within cluster squared distances (toy data)

